

ISic3531

I.Sicily inscription 3531

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Necropolis at the Orti della Maddalena

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3578

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 22 cm

Width 32 cm

Depth 2-2,8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 20 mm

Lines 2 to 5: 25 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) □ M(anibus) □
2. P(ublio) □ Licinio □ Liciniano
3. vixit □ annis □ XXXV
4. Didia □ Pistis □
5. coniugi □ benemereñtti

Apparatus

Text of Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

To the shades of the Underworld. Didia Pistis for her well deserving husband Publius Licinius Licinianus, who lived 35 years.

Translation (it)

Per le ombre dell'aldilà. Didia Pistis per il suo benemerito marito Publius

Licinius Licinianus, che visse 36 anni.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175707

EDR 078346

EDCS 14805806

PHI 313655

Bibliography

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